

Fine-tuning process to Enhance Song Lyrics Prediction in the LyrAics ERC Project

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Abstract

Semantic Textual Similarity (STS) plays a vital role in Natural Language Processing (NLP) as it measures the semantic likeness between two textual excerpts. STS is fundamental to various NLP applications, such as paraphrase identification, document clustering, and information retrieval. As the volume of digital text expands rapidly, creating accurate methods for evaluating semantic similarity becomes essential. Inductive transfer learning, which employs pre-trained models in an unsupervised manner to tackle related tasks, has proven to be a valuable approach for addressing STS challenges. Additionally, the supervised fine-tuning pre-trained language models on domain-specific classification tasks enables researchers to customize these models to target domain features, which would typically necessitate training models from scratch. In this context, this study explores the fine-tuning of multiple language models, including domain-adapted versions, on an STS task involving Spanish song lyrics. The distinct linguistic features and stylistic variations in song lyrics make STS particularly challenging. Our objective is to offer insights into the effectiveness of fine-tuning and domain adaptation for language models in the context of STS with Spanish songs. By assessing the performance of various models and examining the factors contributing to their success, we aim to enhance our understanding of the challenges and opportunities related to applying transfer learning and domain adaptation techniques to the multifaceted world of song lyrics.